

Molecular Confirmation of Plant Viruses Detected by High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) in Fruit Trees Using RT-PCR

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Abstract

This study aimed to confirm the presence of Citrus Exocortis Viroid (CEVd) in *Ficus carica* (fig) trees in the Al-Kufa and Al-Hilla regions of Iraq using a molecular diagnostic approach. Initially, high-throughput sequencing (HTS) data suggested the occurrence of CEVd in symptomatic fig leaf samples. To validate these findings, total RNA was extracted from field-collected samples and subjected to reverse transcription followed by polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) using CEVd-specific primers. The RT-PCR results confirmed the viroid's presence in 30% of the tested samples from Al-Kufa and 28% from Al-Hilla. This molecular confirmation not only supports the HTS data but also marks the first RT-PCR-based detection of CEVd in fig trees in Iraq. The results highlight the need for routine molecular surveillance and suggest a potential involvement of CEVd in fig mosaic disease development in the studied regions.

Keywords: CEVd, RT-PCR, High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS), Plant Viroid detection.

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Introduction

Ficus carica (fig) is considered one of the important fruit-bearing trees in Iraq due to its high nutritional value and adaptability to local environmental conditions, particularly in the central and southern regions of the country. Fig cultivation is widespread in the provinces of Najaf and Babylon, especially in the areas of Al-Kufa and Al-Hilla, where it constitutes a significant component of local agricultural production. However, in recent years, fig cultivation has been increasingly challenged by the emergence and spread of plant diseases, particularly those caused by microscopic pathogens such as viruses and viroids (Sarkhosh *et al.*, 2022; Sabanadzovic *et al.*, 2010). Among the emerging phytopathogens posing a potential threat to fig trees is the Citrus Exocortis Viroid (CEVd), a member of the *Pospiviroidae* family. CEVd is characterized by its remarkably simple molecular structure, consisting of a small, circular, single-stranded RNA molecule lacking a protein coat. Despite this structural simplicity, it exhibits a high capacity for replication within host plant cells and induces distinct pathological symptoms that can result in stunted growth and reduced productivity. While CEVd has traditionally been associated with citrus and tomato plants, recent reports suggest its possible transmission to other plant species, including fig trees. This emerging evidence underscores the need for further research to better understand the viroid's host range and potential impact on non-traditional hosts. (Góra-Sochacka *et al.*, 2024). Conventional diagnostic methods, such as observation of phenotypic symptoms or biological culturing, are limited in accuracy due to the similarity between viroid symptoms and those caused by other diseases or environmental factors. Therefore, molecular diagnostic techniques—such as reverse transcription followed by

polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR)—are currently relied upon, as they provide a precise and rapid means of detecting the presence of viroids in plant tissues, even at early stages of infection or in asymptomatic cases. (Alsharksi et al., 2024). In this context, the present study aims to investigate the presence of Citrus exocortis viroid (CEVd) in fig trees cultivated in the regions of Kufa (Najaf Governorate) and Hillah (Babel Governorate) through the application of reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). The study further seeks to assess the extent of the viroid's distribution within these agriculturally significant areas. This research represents an initial step toward understanding the incidence of CEVd infection in fig trees in Iraq and provides a scientific foundation for developing preventive strategies to safeguard fig orchards, thereby contributing to the stability and sustainability of local agricultural production (Al-Kaeath et al., 2024).

Materials and Methods

Ten samples of fig leaves were collected from the Hillah region and ten samples of fig leaves from the Kufa region, and transferred to the laboratory for ribonucleic acid extraction and RT-PCR tests.

RNA Purification Protocol Procedure

1. Sample Preparation

a) Liquid nitrogen was used to freeze up to 100 mg of fresh or frozen plant tissue after it had been weighed. After being finely powdered, the material was put into a 1.5 or 2 ml centrifuge tube. 10 μ l of β -mercaptoethanol, 100 μ l of PVRS solution, and 1 ml of PVR solution were added. Following mixing, a Thermomixer was used to incubate the sample for 10 minutes at 70°C. The sample was centrifuged for five minutes at 14,000 to 16,000 \times g after incubation.

b) A bead beater was filled with up to 100 mg of frozen or fresh plant tissue. After adding 1 milliliter of PVR solution, 100 microliters of PVRS, and 10 microliters of β -mercaptoethanol to the sample, the combination was well mixed. After being moved to a 1.5 or 2 ml centrifuge tube, the sample was incubated for 10 minutes at 70°C with stirring every three minutes or with a Thermomixer. Following incubation, the sample was centrifuged for five minutes at 14,000–16,000 \times g.

c) Fresh or frozen plant tissue weighing up to 100 mg was put into a homogenization bag. After adding 20 μ l of β -mercaptoethanol and 2 ml of PVR solution, the material was well combined until it was homogenized. Next, 100 μ L of PVRS solution was added to a 1.5 or 2 mL centrifuge tube containing 1 mL of the homogenized mixture. The next step was to use a Thermomixer or incubate at 70°C for 10 minutes, stirring occasionally every three minutes. Following incubation, the sample was centrifuged for five minutes at 14,000–16,000 \times g.

2. RNA Binding

A clean 1.5 or 2 mL centrifuge tube was filled with 450 μ L of the supernatant. After that, 225 μ L of 95–100% ethanol was added.

The liquid with ethanol added was poured onto the PV column, which was then set inside a 2 mL collecting tube.

For one minute, centrifugation was carried out at 14,000–16,000 \times g. After centrifugation, the centrifugation period could be increased until full passage of the material through the PV column membrane was obtained.

The PV column was moved to a fresh collection tube, and the effluent was disposed of. Option 1 for DNA removal: 100 μ L of DNase I enzyme (at a concentration of 2 KU/ml) was added after being dissolved in the proper reaction buffer (for example, 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 10 mM MnCl_2 , and 50

µg/ml BSA at 25°C or using the enzyme's solution). For ten minutes, the sample was allowed to react at room temperature.

3. RNA Wash

1. Add 400 µl of W1 Buffer into the center of the PV Column then centrifuge at 14-16,000 x g for 1 minute.
2. Discard the flow-through then place the PV Column back in the 2 ml Collection Tube.
3. Add 600 µl of Wash Buffer (make sure ethanol was added) to the CENTER of the PV Column.
4. Centrifuge at 14-16,000 x g for 1 minute then discard the flow-through and place the PV Column back in the 2 ml Collection Tube.
5. Add 600 µl of Wash Buffer (make sure ethanol was added) to the CENTER of the PV Column.
6. Centrifuge at 14-16,000 x g for 30 seconds then discard the flow-through and place the PV Column back in the 2 ml Collection Tube.
7. Centrifuge at 14-16,000 x g for 2 minutes to dry the column matrix.

4. RNA Elution

1. Place the dried PV Column in a clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube (RNase-free).
2. Add 50 µl of RNase-free Water or TE (RNase-free) to the CENTER of the column matrix.
3. Let stand for 2 minutes or until the RNase-free Water or TE (RNase-free) is absorbed completely by the matrix.
4. Centrifuge at 14-16,000 x g for 1 minute to elute the purified RNA.

Preparation of Buffers, Solutions

All the buffers and solutions were prepared according to Sambrook and Russell, 2001.

Table 1. Oligonucleotide Primers Sequence Used for RT. PCR Amplification of Specific Gene

Primer's name	Primer's sequences 5' _____ '3	PCR products	Reference
CEVd-F1	ACTGCCGGTGATAAACCGGA	310bp	AL KAEATH <i>et al.</i> , 2024
CEVd-F1	ACTGCCAGTGATATACTGGA		

Preparation of PCR primers

The primers are prepared depending on the manufacturing instruction by dissolving the lyophilized primers with TE (Tris-EDTA) buffer to make stock solution of concentration of 100 pmole/mL.

RNA Electrophoresis

Gel electrophoresis for PCR product

Agarose gel electrophoresis was performed on the amplified products of several genes using a standardized procedure that was modified from Sambrook and Russell (2001). Using a water bath kept at 100°C for about 15 minutes, agarose was first dissolved in 1X TBE buffer to create a 2% (w/v) agarose gel. After allowing the solution to cool to between 50 and 60 degrees Celsius, 2 µL of ethidium bromide (EtBr) was added to the molten gel to help see the DNA.

After pouring the gel mixture into a casting tray with a comb positioned correctly to create wells, the gel was allowed to set for fifteen minutes at room temperature. Ten microliters of each PCR result were

poured into separate wells after the comb was carefully removed once it had set. Additionally, as a molecular size marker, 5 μ L of a 1500 bp DNA ladder was placed into a different well.

After that, the gel was put in an electrophoresis chamber containing 1X TBE buffer inside of it. To improve resolution, an electric current of 110 volts was applied for 30 minutes during the electrophoretic separation process, and then 75 volts for another 60 minutes. Lastly, a transilluminator device was used to see DNA bands under ultraviolet (UV) light.

RT-PCR Procedure

To simplify reaction setup and lower the risk of contamination, One-Step RT-PCR combines PCR and first-strand cDNA synthesis in the same tube. One-Step RT-PCR requires only gene-specific primers. The kit contains TransScript® II RT and TransTaq® HiFi DNA Polymerase. fragment amplification up to 8 kb (see Table 2).

Table 2. RT-PCR Procedure Components

Component	AH411-02 (200 rxns)
TransScript® II One-Step Enzyme Mix	80 μ l
2×One-Step Reaction Mix	2×1 ml
RNase-free Water	2×1 ml

Table 3. Reaction Components

Component	volume	Final concentration
Total RNA	1pg~1 μ g	As required
Forward Primer	0.4 μ l	0.2 μ l
Reverse Primer	0.4 μ l	0.2 μ l
2x One-step Reaction Mix	10 μ l	1x
TransScript® II One-Step Enzyme Mix	0.4 μ l	-
RNase-free Water	Variable Up To 20 μ l	-
Total volume	20 μ l	-

PCR Thermocycling Condition

Thermal cycling conditions for the amplification of each target gene were performed using a conventional PCR thermocycler, as detailed in Table (4). Following the preparation of the PCR master mix, the reaction components were transferred into standard PCR tubes pre-loaded with lyophilized RT-PCR reagents. These lyophilized formulations contained all essential elements required for successful amplification, including reverse transcriptase enzyme, reaction buffer, specific primers, and the RNA template. The tubes were then briefly mixed and centrifuged using an Exispin vortex centrifuge for 3 minutes to ensure proper homogenization. Subsequently, the tubes were placed into the thermocycler to initiate the amplification process.

Table 4. ONE STEP RT-PCR Conditions

PCR step	Temperature	Time	Repeat cycle
cDNA synthesis	45 °C	5 min	1
Initial Denaturation	94 °C	4 min	1
Denaturation	94 °C	30 sec	40
Annealing	50-60 °C	30 sec	
Extension	72°C	1 min	
Final Extension	72°C	7min	1
Hold	4°C	∞	

Results

In this study, a collection of plant samples was obtained from fig tree (*Ficus carica*) leaves across two major agricultural regions in Iraq: Al-Kufa in Najaf Province and Al-Hilla in Babylon Province. The sampling included both symptomatic specimens—exhibiting fig mosaic-like patterns—and asymptomatic ones. This work was conducted during the current growing season with the aim of detecting the presence of Citrus Exocortis Viroid (CEVd) using the reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) technique.

Figure 1. Fig Leaves Collected from the Hillah and Kufa Regions in Southern Iraq Show Symptoms Similar to Those of Fig Mosaic Disease

All samples underwent total RNA extraction using a plant tissue-specific extraction protocol, followed by reverse transcription to synthesize complementary DNA (cDNA). Subsequently, a PCR reaction was performed using specific primers targeting the CEVd sequence. Figure 2 shows the CEVd product, which is 310 base pairs in length, amplified using the TM primer at an annealing temperature of 59°C (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Gel Electrophoresis was Performed to Optimize the PCR Product of Primer Set (CEVd) at Various Temperatures

CEVd exhibited a band of 310 bp. The gel was prepared using a 2% agarose gel and electrophoresed at 110 volts for 15 minutes, followed by a reduction to 75 volts for an additional 60 minutes. Subsequently, the gel was visualized under UV light after staining with Ethidium bromide. Lane L contained a DNA ladder ranging from 100 to 1500 bp.

Figure 3. Electrophoretic Visualization of PCR Amplicons Using CEVd-Specific Primers

Agarose gel electrophoresis analysis of PCR products amplified with CEVd-specific primers targeting a 310 bp fragment. Amplification was performed with an annealing temperature of 59°C. The separation was conducted on a 1.5% agarose gel for 15 minutes at 110 V, followed by 60 minutes at 75 V. DNA bands were visualized under ultraviolet light after staining with ethidium bromide. Lane L contains the DNA size marker (ranging from 100 to 1500 bp). Lanes 4 and 5 exhibit positive amplification signals, while lanes 1 to 3 show no detectable bands, indicating negative results. Lane N corresponds to the negative control reaction.

Molecular amplification assays (RT-PCR) revealed that approximately 30% of the samples collected from the Kufa region tested positive for the presence of the viroid, with 6 out of 20 analyzed specimens exhibiting amplification signals. In comparison, the infection rate in the Hilla region was estimated at 28%, as viroid-specific sequences were identified in 5 out of 18 tested samples (Table 5).

Table 5. Number of Samples Examined and the Number of Samples Infected with CEVd Viroid Using the RT-PCR Technique

Geographical Area	Number of Samples	Infected Samples	Infection percentage
Hillah	18	5	% 27.5
Kufa	20	6	%30

The positive results were validated through agarose gel electrophoresis, which revealed a distinct amplification band corresponding to the expected size of the CEVd sequence. This provides clear evidence of the viroid's genetic material in the analyzed samples. These findings represent a significant indication of CEVd presence in Iraqi fig orchards, even though some infected samples exhibited mild or non-specific symptoms. This underscores the critical role of molecular diagnostics as a more reliable tool than solely relying on visual field assessments. Notably, certain samples that tested positive were collected from trees displaying no obvious symptoms such as stunting or stem cracking, suggesting the presence of latent infections or early stages of disease development. These observations are consistent with the findings reported by Negahban et al. (2024) and Al Kaeath et al.(2024) .

It is noteworthy that this study represents the first scientific report employing RT-PCR for the detection of CEVd in fig plants within Iraq. Previous reports have primarily relied on high-throughput sequencing (NGS) technologies, which, while offering high accuracy, are often cost-prohibitive and technically demanding for routine diagnostic applications (Al Kaeath et al., 2024). The successful implementation of RT-PCR in this investigation marks a significant step toward the development of practical diagnostic protocols. Such protocols could be effectively integrated into agricultural monitoring and disease management programs, as emphasized by Kuan Wu in 2024.

Discussion

The findings obtained in this study demonstrate the actual occurrence of Citrus Exocortis Viroid (CEVd) infection in fig trees (*Ficus carica*) from the regions of Kufa and Hilla, with infection rates of 30% and 28%, respectively. This discovery is of considerable significance, not only due to the confirmed presence of CEVd in Iraqi fig orchards, but also because it represents the first documented detection of this viroid using RT-PCR in Iraq. This establishes RT-PCR as a rapid and reliable molecular diagnostic tool. These findings align with those of Al Kaeath et al. (2024), who employed next-generation sequencing (NGS) in their study during the same year.

When compared with prior studies that utilized NGS for CEVd detection, the current results corroborate the viroid's presence in the Iraqi agricultural context. However, this study further demonstrates that RT-

PCR offers a practical and cost-effective alternative for viroid surveillance, particularly in routine surveys and diagnostic laboratories with limited resources. RT-PCR's ability to detect infections in asymptomatic plant samples underscores its value for early detection and disease management.

Notably, the viroid was detected not only in trees showing visible symptoms but also in apparently healthy specimens. This suggests the presence of latent infections or low viroid titers that cannot be identified through field observations alone. Such findings highlight the limitations of visual diagnosis and reinforce the necessity of incorporating molecular diagnostic techniques into plant health monitoring programs.

The occurrence of CEVd in a crop of economic importance such as fig may have long-term implications for fruit quality and overall productivity, especially in the absence of effective preventive measures. Potential sources of infection include traditional propagation practices, use of non-sterilized agricultural tools (e.g., pruning equipment), and the planting of already-infected seedlings.

Accordingly, the results of this study go beyond mere detection; they emphasize the urgent need for a national framework that includes early diagnostic strategies, periodic monitoring, and implementation of proper agricultural practices. This is especially critical as fig cultivation continues to expand across various regions of Iraq.

Conclusions

Citrus Exocortis Viroid (CEVd) was detected in fig samples from Kufa and Hilla using RT-PCR, marking the first application of this molecular approach for viroid identification in Iraq. Infection rates were 30% in Kufa and 28% in Hilla, indicating that the viroid is not isolated but rather present in the broader agricultural environment. RT-PCR proved effective even in detecting infections in asymptomatic plants, making it a valuable tool for early-stage diagnosis. This underscores the importance of targeting sources such as contaminated propagation material and unsterilized tools, which may facilitate viroid transmission among trees. Based on these findings, the study recommends the adoption of RT-PCR as a standard diagnostic tool within national fig health surveillance programs. Additionally, regular surveys covering a wider range of agricultural zones should be conducted to better understand the spread of the viroid and identify infection hotspots. The establishment of a national viroid infection database for horticultural crops is also advised to support informed decision-making and guide strategic disease management efforts.

References

- Al-Kaeath, N., Zagier, S., Alisawi, O., Al Fadhal, F., & Mahfoudhi, N. (2024). High-Throughput Sequencing Identified Multiple Fig Viruses and Viroids Associated with Fig Mosaic Disease in Iraq. *The Plant Pathology Journal*, 40(5), 486-497. <https://doi.org/10.5423/PPJ.OA.04.2024.0068>
- Sarkhosh, A., Yavari, A., & Ferguson, L. (Eds.). (2022). *The fig: Botany, production and uses*. CABI.
- Sabanadzovic, S., Abou Ghanem-Sabanadzovic, N., & Gallitelli, D. (2010). Detection and molecular characterization of *Citrus exocortis viroid* in fig (*Ficus carica*). *Journal of Plant Pathology*, 92(3), 807-812.
- Góra-Sochacka, A. (2004). Viroids: Unusual small pathogenic RNAs. *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, 51(3), 587-607.
- Negahban, H., Bolboli, Z., & Mostowfizadeh-Ghalemfarsa, R. (2024). Development of PCR-based assays for the detection of the evident and latent infection with *Stilbocrea banibashemiana*, the causal agent of fruit tree cankers. *Crop Protection*, 181, 106677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2024.106677>

- Alsharksi, A. N., Sirekbasan, S., Gürkök-Tan, T., & Mustapha, A. (2024). From tradition to innovation: Diverse molecular techniques in the fight against infectious diseases. *Diagnostics*, *14*(24), 2876. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics14242876>
- Wu, K., Li, D., & Wu, Y. (2024). Development of a multiplex RT-PCR for simultaneous detection of five *Actinidia* viruses. *Agronomy*, *14*(8), 1650. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy14081650>
- Chambers, A. H., et al. (2023). A reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification assay for the detection of *Citrus exocortis viroid* in Australian citrus. *Australasian Plant Pathology*, *52*, 121-132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13313-023-00914-3>
- Wu, C.-F., et al. (2015). Multiplex detection, distribution, and genetic diversity of Hop stunt viroid and *Citrus exocortis viroid* infecting citrus in Taiwan. *Virology Journal*, *12*, 64. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12985-015-0276-5>
- Ragozzino, E., Faggioli, F., & Barba, M. (2005). Distribution of *Citrus exocortis viroid* and *Hop stunt viroid* in citrus orchards of central Italy as revealed by one-tube one-step RT-PCR. *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*, *44*(3), 322-326.

